

COLORIMETRIC DETECTION AND ESTIMATION OF CERIUM

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Quadrivalent cerium gives a bright yellow colour with benzidine in hydrochloric acid solution. 0.037 of the element can be detected on a spot-plate. Trivalent rare earths, Th, Cu, Be, Mg, alkaline earths, Zn, Al, Bi, UO_2^{++} , Mn, Ni, NO_3' , PO_4''' , Cl', F', MoO_4'' , As_2O_4'' , in moderate amounts do not interfere; but, vanadate and chromate cause interference even in small quantities. The reagent may also be adopted for the colorimetric estimation of cerium.

According to Feigl (*Oesterr. chem. Ztg.*, 1919, 22, 124) quadrivalent cerium gives a green coloration with benzidine in acetic acid solution and by comparative tests with other rare earths Herzfeld (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1939, 115, 421) showed that the test was specific for cerium and the green colour was noticeable with 0.062 mg. of the element. By far the most sensitive reagent for this element appears to be leucomalachite green (*Mikrochemie*, 1936, 21, 35) which is reported to show the presence of 0.03 γ cerium. Other reagents of intermediate sensitivity are known (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1939, 6, 889; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1934, 217, 272; *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1937, 9, 181; *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 1479); but in most of these cases the reagent may not be adopted for quantitative estimation. It has been found, however, that benzidine in the presence of hydrochloric acid gives a bright yellow colour with quadrivalent cerium and as little as 0.3 γ of the element can be easily recognised on a spot-plate. Further, trivalent cerium does not give this reaction and a number of elements, viz., other trivalent rare earths, Th, Cu, Be, Mg, alkaline earths, Zn, Al, Bi, UO_2^{++} , Mn, Ni, NO_3' , PO_4''' , Cl', F', MoO_4'' , As_2O_4'' , in moderate amounts do not interfere; but vanadate and chromate cause interference even in small quantities. The presence of large amounts of sulphate should be avoided, since SO_4'' reacts with benzidine base to form a white crystalline precipitate which would interfere with colour comparison.

The reagent may also be adopted for exact determinations of the element for amounts varying from 0.02 mg. to 0.25 mg. in 50 ml. provided that measurements are made sufficiently quickly, as the yellow colour fades with time. This property also necessitates the use of an external colour standard for comparison.

EXPERIMENTAL

The following solutions were prepared :

- (i) 0.1% Benzidine in 0.3N hydrochloric acid.
- (ii) About 0.1rg. ferric chloride ($FeCl_3, 6H_2O$) dissolved in 100 ml. of 2N-HCl as the standard for comparison of colour.
- (iii) Standard ceric sulphate containing 0.290 mg. of cerium in 100 ml. of 0.5N sulphuric acid.
- (iv) Test solution in 0.5N sulphuric acid containing 0.4 to 6 mg. of cerium in 100 ml.

To standardise the ferric chloride solution 5 ml. of solution (iii) were taken in a 50 ml. measuring flask; 1 ml. of (i) was added, shaken, and quickly made up to the mark with 3N hydrochloric acid, and compared in a colorimeter.

To make an estimation 5 ml. of the test solution were taken in a 50 ml. measuring flask, 1 ml. of the benzidine reagent was added, made up to the mark with 3*N* hydrochloric acid and compared with the standard ferric chloride solution. The following results were obtained with solutions of known cerium content.

TABLE I

Ce taken.	Ce found.	Ce taken.	Ce found.
0.023 mg.	0.022 mg.	0.116 mg.	0.120 mg.
0.035	0.034	0.145	0.145
0.046	0.046	0.174	0.171
0.058	0.059	0.200	0.191
0.125	0.120	0.232	0.231

Fading of the yellow colour with time has also been investigated. In the accompanying diagram the reciprocal of the depth of the colour, which is a measure of the apparent concentration of the element, is plotted against time. Curve (a) refers to a concentration of 0.116 mg. of cerium and curve (b) to 0.125 mg. in 50 ml. It will

be seen that no appreciable error is likely to be introduced if the measurements are concluded within 2 minutes. Curves for various concentrations lie parallel to one another. When the curve is extrapolated to zero time and these latter values are adopted, better agreement with the standard is obtained. The values thus calculated are shown below.

TABLE II

Ce taken.	Ce found.	Ce taken.	Ce found.
0.023 mg.	0.023 mg.	0.116	0.117
0.046	0.047	0.125	0.126